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ESG- :

ESG-LEASING: A NEW ERA OF SUSTAINABLE FINANCE

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ESG- ESG-
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: ESG- , « » , ESG

The article explores the concept of ESG-leasing as an innovative tool for sustainable financing that integrates environmental, social and management principles. The advantages and challenges of ESG-criteria integration into leasing activity are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the impact of ESG-leasing on companies' environmental responsibility, resource optimization and formation of sustainable partnerships. The article emphasizes the importance of ESG-leasing for achieving the goals of sustainable development and increasing the competitiveness of enterprises in the modern economy.

Keywords: ESG-leasing, financing, green economy, ESG initiatives.

17 (ESG) (—) 2015 ,

ESG- « »
1. , ESG- (Environmental).

CO2 « »

2. (Social).

3. (Governance).

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- ESG- ESG- ;
- ESG- (ESG),
- ESG- () .
- (—) ESG- ,
- 55% 2030 1990
- ESG- , ,
- (The European Green Deal), 2050 .
- « (Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive — CSRD).
- ESG (European Sustainability Reporting Standards — ESRS).
- « » ,
- » [2]; (Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation — SFDR).
- ESG (Due Diligence).
- (Apple
- ; H&M ;
- Nestl ,) .
- .

ESG, :
• Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB): SASB

• Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD):

• Global Reporting Initiative (GRI),

(CSE),

(ESG)

ESG-

, 87%

GRI,
, 63%

, 56%

TCFD

SASB

2023

and Exchange Act — FIEA)

(Financial Instruments

TCFD, 2027

(ISSB)

(SSBJ).

Action plan for carbon dioxide peaking before 2030 —

: 2030

65%

25%,
2005

2060 [4].

1.

ESG.

7%

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[1]).

BMW

ESG-

Siemens

, ESG-

Gucci,

ESG-

Gucci

CO2

\$7,500,

Investment Tax Credit

30%

2023

62%

10

75 / CO².

€9,000

€10,000

€6,750

€45,000,

€2,500

€7,000

50%

60

[6].

(— EIB)

EC,

2024 EIB

1,5

(,), (JEI)

8,7 2023

8,76 2024 [3].

2028 9 .(.3).

ESG-

- LeasePlan (): LeasePlan
- Arval (): Arval, BNP Paribas,
- Sixt (): Sixt, Tesla
- Hertz (): Hertz, Tesla, Polestar
- ALD Automotive (): ALD Automotive

(.4).

.4.
[7].

2024 (

15%, 10% 2%

2023

19 2025 Octopus Electric Vehicles
(salary sacrifice),
«Clean Energy for All»

2.

ESG,

Siemens Financial Services

BT Group

ESG-

IT-

ESG-

HSBC

BNP Paribas Lease Group

ESG-

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IKEA

IT-

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2025

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